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Updated assessment of developments and revision of scientific challenge - Optimising Magnetically Confined Plasmas with GENE

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the progress made for the gyrokinetic fusion turbulence code GENE-X since the last deliverable. The advancements are mainly threefold. First, we progressed on the GPU port of the code so that it can now be run fully on the GPU in a performant way. Second, the employed field solver library PARALLAX[1] is now also fully ported to GPUs via the backend PAccX[2]. Additional work has been invested in making the fieldsolver available on AMD GPUs and to employ a library solution instead of the self-written FGMRES-Multigrid solver. Third, the implementation of the block-structured grids reached a level of usability on the CPU which makes it possible to reduce the number of gridpoints by a factor of 4-8.

It is not yet possible to combine all of the achievements, but with using the GPU code for GENE-X and the fieldsolver, we arrive at a FOM of around 20000 on 32 MI300A GPUs. The roadmap has been refined to further close the gap to the envisaged FOM of 6000.

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1 Introduction

GENE and GENE-X are grid-based microturbulence simulation codes solving the gyrokinetic Vlasov-Maxwell system of integro-differential equations. Both codes work on a 5D physical grid consisting of three spatial coordinates and two velocity space coordinates, the velocity along the field lines v_{\parallel} and the magnetic moment μ . Whereas GENE uses a field aligned coordinate system with the spatial coordinates x (radial), y (binormal) and z (along the field line), GENE-X employs a fieldline-coordinate independent (FCI) approach. The latter uses the cylindrical coordinate system R , Z and ϕ in real space and the same velocity coordinates as GENE.

Both codes have two main parts, first the computation of the right-hand side of the Vlasov equations which mainly consists of stencil operations in different directions and the computation of the nonlinearity (which involves 1D FFTs in the case of GENE). The second important part is the solution of the field equations which are linear equations solved in all poloidal planes independently. The input to these equations are the zeroth (density) and first (parallel current) moment of the distribution function, which are computed by a reduction (MPI_Allreduce) operation over the velocity space.

In previous deliverables (D1.2 and D1.6), we have shown the shortcomings of the two codes and first solutions with respect to the target challenge. One of the biggest tasks is to port the GENE-X code to work on GPUs and this task has been progressed a lot in the last year. A second task has been the optimization of the fieldsolver scaling in the velocity space directions. As a predecessor step to this scaling optimization, we focused on running the fieldsolver on GPUs on all available GPU architectures. A highly optimized fieldsolver takes away some pressure from the scaling needs. But still, improvements of the velocity space scaling will be a main focus in the remaining 18 months of the project.

The third point shown in D1.2 was the problem of strongly varying background temperature which leads either to too many points or to an underresolution in velocity space. To overcome this problem, we originally wanted to develop a library to be used by both GENE codes, but finally refrained from this solution and focused on a specific implementation for the GENE-X code. The GENE code already supports block-structured grids (at least on the CPU).

As described in the former two deliverables, GENE-X is the most time-consuming part of the simulation, so we focus in this deliverable on the progress of this code towards the scientific challenge.

2 Current Status of Scientific Challenge

The Scientific Challenge is not changed. We still head for an ab-initio prediction of density and temperature profiles in the ITER tokamak using the three codes GENE for the core, TANGO for the transport evolution and GENE-X for the edge to the wall part. We refer for a detailed description of the physical and numerical setup of the scientific target case to Deliverable D1.2.

3 Code Developments

3.1 GPU offloading and optimization efforts in GENE-X

3.1.1 General GPU porting progress

The main code development results have been published in a recent paper titled "OpenACC and OpenMP-Accelerated Fortran/C++ Gyrokinetic Fusion Code GENE-X for Heterogeneous Architectures" [3]. It has been accepted to the Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing Conference (PASC) 2025.

This paper covers mainly two points. First, the interoperation efforts between the main Fortran layer and the auxiliary C++ layer of GENE-X and second, the GPU offloading efforts of GENE-X via OpenACC and OpenMP offload. Both directive-based approaches use very similar concepts, just the syntax is different. The largest difference is the portability aspect, as OpenMP is much more widely portable across different GPU vendors, e.g., NVIDIA, AMD, Intel, than OpenACC. Both directives are implemented in GENE-X, but we will focus in the project on the more portable OpenMP offload set of directives.

This paper excludes topics related to field solvers that are powered by PARALLAX and its PAccX libraries. It also excludes comparisons with kernels running on Fortran OpenMP on the CPU. The excluded field solver regions are relevant parts of the code, but even without it the results are important as the native regions of the application side take most of the computing time on the CPU. All benchmarks and performance comparisons in the paper are done strictly within the auxiliary C++ layer. All benchmark cases used in the paper are based on the production run of TCV-X21 tokamak published in [4] and are run on MareNostrum 5 ACC partition with 4 NVIDIA H100 per node.

Figure 1: Runtime comparison published in [3].

One benchmark case used in the paper has a size of 5.4 billion grid points and is spread across 80 MPI processes and 80 GPUs to get an overview of the performance gain from GPU offloading. This makes up a quarter of the total grid size in [4] but the size per MPI process is eight times larger. In summary, we achieve a speedup of $6.9\times$ with OpenMP Target offload directives in the elapsed time of the timestep as shown in Figure 1. The three main operators or compute kernels, i.e., `Vlasov static`, `Vlasov dynamic` and `BGK collision`, all together gain a significant speedup of $21\times$.

In the paper, a different case with 212,387 grid points on a single GPU with an MPI

Figure 2: Roofline model of OpenACC and OpenMP offload kernels in GENE-X from [3] provided by NVIDIA Nsight Compute on MareNostrum5.

process provides us with the roofline model as shown in Figure 2. This figure shows that all GENE-X compute kernels are memory-bound by the 1631 GB/s bandwidth of GPU high-bandwidth memory (HBM). The roofline model also shows that the default configuration of OpenMP offload performs slightly better than OpenACC. After we see some of the metrics related to the L1 and L2 caches provided by Nsight Compute, we conclude that OpenMP offload performs better for memory-bound kernels with coalesced access and high cache reuse, as the default configuration results in better memory access pattern and warp occupancy.

Figure 3: Strong scaling of the runtime and GPU speedup factor published in [3].

Figure 3 shows the strong scaling of OpenMP on CPUs, OpenACC and OpenMP offload on GPUs. Information on the grid size and the MPI decomposition is provided in Table 1. The same case as the overview case in Figure 1 cannot be incorporated in this strong scaling analysis due to the 64 GB GPU memory limit when we try to run the same size within one node. Therefore, these cases were chosen so that the one-node case can fit into GPU memory. This also motivates the GPU memory optimization

efforts reported in the next two sections. The compute kernels on GPUs show similar performance improvements compared to the ones on CPUs as the number of GPUs used is increased. However, ghost exchange and synchronization time become more prominent as bottlenecks when more GPUs are used. The speedup factors from GPU offloading are diminished as a result of the increasing contribution of the bottlenecks. However, the speedup factor of the Vlasov static operator is slightly increasing.

Table 1: Problem size and MPI decomposition for the strong scaling analysis in Figure 3 [3].

Dim.	Num. points	MPI processes for each case							
RZ	212387	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
φ	8	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	8
v_{\parallel}	24	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
μ	12	1	1	2	4	8	16	16	
species α	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
Number of MPI processes		4	8	16	32	64	128	256	
Number of GPUs		4	8	16	32	64	128	256	
Number of nodes		1	2	4	8	16	32	64	

In Figure 1 and Figure 3, we observe a significant runtime contribution from the communication regions, especially the synchronization time of `MPI_Allreduce`. Focusing on `MPI_Allreduce`, the overwhelming synchronization time compared to the pure communication time may also indicate a similar phenomenon for the ghost exchange region. However, we cannot isolate the pure communication time easily with non-blocking MPI communications. This indicates some load imbalances occurring during the timestep, but the damage is observed mainly in the region of blocking communication, e.g. `MPI_Allreduce`. Due to this, the total performance is undermined by load imbalances that become stronger as the compute kernels become faster by the GPU offloading. We find that the synchronization time of a central collective communication routine (`MPI_Allreduce`) takes more than 50% of the time per timestep in the OpenMP offload cases for the cases with 16 or 32 GPUs in Figure 3. This bottleneck is then followed by the ghost exchange which takes approximately 16%.

Outside the scope of the paper, we have performed a preliminary investigation to find the source of the load imbalances in GENE-X. We have extended our built-in profiler in GENE-X to support tracing of the runtime. GENE-X built-in profiler only stores cumulative performance data such as total runtime, number of calls, and time per call for each profiling region. We recently extended the capability of our built-in profiler, to store all the timestamps for each start and stop instances of all profiling regions. This allows us to construct a trace view of the profiling regions in GENE-X. The trace file in `csv` format not only can be visualized our homemade visualization script, which can show the profiler regions of each MPI process, but can also be converted to `json` format according to the Perfetto scheme and visualized by the Perfetto-UI web interface. Figure 4 is the trace visualization generated by our script and it demonstrates the load imbalance caused by one of our diagnostic I/O, i.e., `diagnose_em_fields`. The mitigation of the

load imbalance, which has been found only recently, is part of our roadmap to improve the code’s performance.

Figure 4: GENE-X runtime trace of 80 MPI processes from the built-in tracer visualized with our native interactive visualizer.

3.1.2 AMD GPU support

The porting of the code to GPUs is only one step. For usage of the code on a wide range of GPU based supercomputers, portability and especially performance portability is a big point. The main development took place on NVIDIA GPUs due to the mature software ecosystem there, which eases the development. So a next step is to support GPUs from AMD, which are employed in LUMI, but also in MPG’s inhouse system VIPER-GPU. The OpenMP Target offload directive approach is in principle portable as it is defined in the OpenMP 4.5 and following standard. But to produce performance GPU kernels out of the code annotated by directives, a compiler is needed that supports this step. At the moment for NVIDIA GPUs this is only possible with the `nvc++` compiler and for AMD GPUs with the `amdclang++` compiler.

We are able to run GENE-X with OpenMP Offload on AMD GPUs by compiling the code with the combination of `gfortran` and `amdclang++` in contrast of `gfortran` and `nvc++` combination on NVIDIA GPUs. A pure compilation with either `nvfortran` on NVIDIA based systems or `amdflang` on AMD based systems is not yet possible due to compiler problems with the modern Fortran employed in the code. So we have to rely on a combination of `gfortran` for the CPU Fortran code and a C++ compiler that translates the OpenMP Target offload directives to performant GPU kernels.

From our experience, our build setup and GPU implementation of GENE-X on AMD GPUs seems to be still less reliable than that on NVIDIA GPUs. On NVIDIA GPUs, the OpenACC and OpenMP offload implementations of GENE-X are well unit tested for debug and release build mode. Their order of convergence are also well tested via method of manufactured solutions (MMS) as shown in [3]. However on AMD GPUs, the Vlasov static operator still fails our unit test when it is built with debug mode. This has been observed both on Viper-GPU with AMD MI300A GPUs and LUMI-G with AMD MI250x GPUs. Surprisingly it works well when build with optimization in release mode. The Vlasov static operator is the largest and the most complex operator in GENE-X so far thus we presume it has many room of improvements both in term of performance and portability.

Figure 5: Roofline model of OpenMP offload kernels in GENE-X provided by AMD OmniPerf on LUMI-G.

On the EuroHPC LUMI-G machine, the software stack is provided by HPE-Cray Programming Environment (PE). This software stack seems to not easily support our mixed compiler setup. Even after some workarounds and the help of LUMI experts during a hackathon, we only managed to run GENE-X on a single process and a single GPU with only the release build mode. Moreover, the fieldsolver library PARALLAX seems to trigger some unidentified compiler bugs in `gfortran/13` when a numerical equilibrium is used, i.e., TCV-X21 or ITER equilibrium. Our code can run normally with `gfortran/12` or older and `gfortran/14`. However, LUMI software stack does not have GNU modules of these versions. In conclusion, we have yet able to run anything close to production runs on LUMI-G. On the other hand, we managed to generate a preliminary roofline model shown in Figure 5 with AMD OmniPerf on LUMI-G.

3.1.3 Optimization: GPU memory usage

From our experiences so far, we have realized that GPU offloading of GENE-X has one limitation other than the performance. This limitation is the GPU memory limit. Marenostrium 5 NVIDIA H100 has 64 GB of HBM per GPU and Viper-GPU MI300A has 128 GB of HBM per GPU. In GENE-X, we have a policy to keep data on GPU as long as possible to eliminate communication overheads between CPU and GPU. Since we have multiple 5D distribution functions in double precision, GENE-X can easily try to subscribe more GPU memory than the limit. While MPI decomposition can be done on φ , v_{\parallel} , mu , and species dimensions, full RZ plane cannot be decomposed, which means that we will face this memory cap issue when we try to reach our target case.

Figure 6: Device memory optimization related to `mailbox_t`.

We have investigated the GPU memory limit issue in GENE-X and found several GPU memory optimization opportunities without compromising on zero CPU-GPU memory latency during time integration on GENE-X side. To investigate GPU memory usage, we have developed a built-in GPU memory tracer in GENE-X. In GENE-X, we have built-in GPU memory sanitizer after every memory allocation and deallocation on GPU. Since the datatype and the number of array elements are passed to the sanitizer, we extended the sanitizer to calculate the memory size and log it together with the timestamps. This results in a simple built-in GPU memory tracer. Since the tracer does not intercept the driver such as using CUPTI on NVIDIA GPUs to measure the GPU memory usage, the sanitizer and tracer rely heavily on the developer to instrument the code properly. This also means that we cannot trace GPU memory usage from libraries that we use including PARALLAX/PAccX. However, this solution has negligible overheads in terms of runtime and memory, which is not true with tools such as Nsight System. It also annotates the GPU memory traces with region names, such as the class name itself in GENE-X. The traces can be visualized with our visualization script as shown in Figure 6. The vertical gaps seen in the figure is a result of an unintended bug of our visualizer, not the tracer itself.

By using our built-in GPU memory tracer, we can see the GPU memory high-watermark and the class that consume memory the most. In the left figure of Figure 6, we can see that there are multiple `mailbox_t` instances that consume a non-negligible amount of memory. `mailbox_t` contains buffer arrays that facilitate ghost/halo exchanges, which means that they are only needed during the ghost/halo exchanges, yet the figure shows that `mailbox_t` resides on GPU memory throughout the whole time integration. We then optimized the `mailbox_t` to allocate the buffers to GPU memory only during ghost/halo exchanges, we managed to reduce the GPU memory high-watermark from 14.4 GB to 10.4 GB (26.5%) as shown in the right figure of Figure 6. Moreover, as shown in the figure, 10.4 GB is only the high-watermark, which means that the time integration on average uses less GPU memory, which is around 9.3 GB. Since ghost/halo exchange does not overlap with the solver calls, the solvers can occupy around 1 GB extra room to use the GPU memory; thus this reduces the overall GPU-memory high-watermark even more with GPU-accelerated field solvers. There are still other possible memory optimizations that we are currently investigating, such as memory optimization in the case of axisymmetric simulation, which is typical in tokamak simulation.

3.1.4 Optimization: GENE-X support for PARALLAX’s mesh reordering

PARALLAX has a mesh reordering feature on the poloidal (RZ) plane that leverages Morton Z-order space-filling curves. We recently developed the support for this feature on GENE-X that can work on the Fortran layer on CPUs, C++ layer on CPUs and GPUs with minimum overheads. We experimented with several mesh reordering sizes, e.g., 4, 8, 16, 32, and 64, and the runtime breakdown is shown in Table 2 performed with OpenMP offload on 16 GPUs. The zero reordering size refers to a case where reordering is not performed. The number of points used here are $(N_{RZ}, N_{\varphi}, N_{v_{\parallel}}, N_{\mu}, N_{\text{species}}) = (339411, 16, 40, 10, 2)$ and are decomposed into number of processes (1, 2, 2, 2, 2), respectively. For example, we managed to gain 22% speedup by reordering the mesh with size 4. 3.6 times speedup of the ghost exchange contributes to the overall performance gain.

Both the Ohm’s law and Maxwell’s equation solvers gain $1.2\times$ speedup. The Vlasov static is the operator in GENE-X that contains stencil operations on the RZ dimension, yet it only gains 5% speedup.

Table 2: Runtime per timestep per MPI process comparisons of different regions in GENE-X with respect to the mesh reordering size with OpenMP offload.

	Runtime [s] w.r.t to mesh reordering size					
	0	4	8	16	32	64
Timestep	18.424	14.282	17.987	14.203	17.575	17.406
Ghost exchange	2.993	0.842	1.709	1.080	1.835	2.639
Vlasov static	1.206	1.148	1.143	1.151	1.153	1.157
Vlasov dynamic	0.056	0.056	0.056	0.056	0.056	0.056
Collision	0.759	1.376	3.399	1.003	3.036	1.766
Solver Ohm	1.161	0.979	1.030	0.985	1.010	1.054
Solver Maxwell	12.180	9.812	10.581	9.859	10.416	10.665

To see the effect of mesh reordering in more detail, we performed the same experiment with 0 and 4 reorder sizes while comparing between Fortran and C++ kernels with OpenMP of CPUs. The results are shown in Table 3. The overall performance gain from the mesh reordering is not so different between Fortran and C++. However, the Fortran Vlasov static operator gains almost 2 times speedup, whereas the C++ kernel gains only $1.34\times$ speedup. The Fortran version of this operator is generally less optimized than C++ one. For example, it needs to be manually collapsed while the C++ version does not need such kind of manual loop transformation. The mesh reordering may help the Fortran version more and gives larger gain but this does not necessarily mean that it is more optimized as this can be seen from the runtime difference between the two. It also seems that the compiler optimization and OpenMP library in C++ does a better job in reusing the cache than the Fortran compiler even without the reordering. However, this difference might also be caused by different compiler vendors and thus different compiler optimization. Moreover, both gains are much higher than the GPU one. This might hint at already well optimized cache reuse by OpenMP offload or there are more prominent overheads that hide the spatial locality advantage. Since the Vlasov static operator is the largest and most complex operator in GENE-X, kernel splitting may help us in investigating the effect of mesh reordering in more detail together with memory-related metrics from NVIDIA’s Nsight Compute kernel profiling tool such as L1/TEX and L2 cache hit rates.

3.2 Block-structured grids for GENE-X

GENE-X utilizes fixed velocity space grids ($v_{||}$ and μ) to predict the density and temperature profiles for the target ITER case. Due to the significant temperature differences across the profiles, a large number of grid points are required to adequately resolve all regions, making simulations computationally expensive. The Block-Structured Grids (BSG) method offers a solution by efficiently reducing the number of grid points while

Table 3: Runtime comparisons of timestep (left) and Vlasov static operator (right) in GENE-X with respect to the mesh reordering size with OpenMP on CPUs.

timestep	Reorder size			static	Reorder size		
	0	4	speedup		0	4	speedup
F90	204.973	163.506	1.25	F90	29.055	14.746	1.97
C++	49.626	38.637	1.28	C++	5.248	3.92	1.34

maintaining accuracy. The idea of BSG is to subdivide the radial direction in a small number of blocks and change the extent of the velocity space grids in dependence of the background temperature, but keep the same number of grid points. With this approach, which has been first implemented for GENE in ref.[5, 6], we can reach a high resolution with a fixed number of grid points for the price of a more complicated implementation and necessary interpolation at the block boundaries.

Figure 7 gives a rough picture of the BSG block representation in GENE-X. In figure 7a, which represents the real space in RZ coordinates, the radial domain is subdivided into two blocks. In figure 7b, a corresponding representation of the poloidal plane in the v_{\parallel} space is provided with the y-axis representing radial direction based on the RZ coordinates. The region close to the core (colored red in real space) will have a higher temperature and will therefore have a wider domain in the velocity space compared to the lower temperature region (colored green in real space) which has a relatively narrow domain. With this setup, when same number of grid points is used in velocity space, we can satisfy the resolution requirements at every radial point in the temperature profile. However, as evident from figure 7b, the grid lines across the blocks will not be aligned, therefore, we require interpolations when derivatives along the radial direction are evaluated.

Figure 7: Representational BSG blocks in the real and velocity space.

Apart from the obvious reduction in the number of velocity space points, the BSG

algorithm implemented in GENE-X possesses a few more advantages. Firstly, the underlying numerics used in GENE-X will not be altered with respect to the velocity space discretizations. Secondly, the implementation itself is minimally invasive which allows for continued usage of the existing optimized routines. Finally, as a side effect, we can also expect reduced storage requirements for checkpoints, diagnostics and other I/O related data.

To quantify the theoretical reduction in grid points in v_{\parallel} space for the target ITER case, we find that it is proportional to the temperature ratio,

$$\frac{N_{BSG}^{v_{\parallel}}}{N_{SG}^{v_{\parallel}}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{1}{T_{ratio}}} \quad (1)$$

Here, T_{ratio} represents the temperature ratio between the temperature at the core and the edge which is around 100. $N_{SG}^{v_{\parallel}}$ represents the case without BSG and $N_{BSG}^{v_{\parallel}}$ is for the BSG case. From equation 1, we can expect a point reduction of up to 10 times lesser than the non-BSG case. Additionally, we can also expect further reduction in μ direction as the point reduction varies linearly with the temperature ratio, $N_{BSG}^{\mu}/N_{SG}^{\mu} \approx 1/T_{ratio}$. This extent of point reduction should certainly improve FOM and successfully help simulate the targeted ITER case.

The implementation of BSG is mainly concentrated in two components of GENEX: the mesh class and the several numerical operators that have a velocity space dependency. To achieve this, we developed two main classes in the BSG module: the grid generation class and the operator class. The grid generation class of BSG is integrated with the existing GENEX mesh class. Depending on the user BSG input specifying the block divisions and the corresponding velocity space information, we generate the required grids in the GENEX mesh class. Since the number of points in the velocity space remains constant, we note that there is no requirement of modifying the velocity space grid generation implementation in GENEX, essentially allowing us to reuse the existing routines.

Next, the grids generated using BSG need to be integrated to the operators where there are operations in velocity space. To accommodate this, we developed a BSG operator class. This class is developed to achieve two main objectives. First, provide the required velocity space information for points on RZ grids which now have a block dependency based on the temperature. A second more complex requirement we address is for cases where derivatives are evaluated in RZ directions in velocity space. For the most part, we use the velocity space information and perform stencil operations as done originally in GENEX. However, for stencils that span across block boundaries need interpolations, this class provides the required routines which can be easily integrated into the GENEX operators.

The work on the BSG has reached two major milestones. The CPU backed of GENE-X has been fully adapted to use the BSG routines. Further, the implemented CPU code has been verified through Method of Manufactured Solutions (MMS) which is the primary integration test setup used in GENE-X. Figure 8 represents the code verification results performed through MMS. The resolutions used in these tests generally vary from 1 million grid points to 14 Billion points (the grid includes RZ points, v_{\parallel} , μ , ϕ and species). These plots suggest that the stencil operations along the radial direction combined with the interpolations near the block boundaries still follow the expected order of accuracy.

Figure 8: Convergence study with MMS: Observed order of accuracy for distribution function and field derivatives, compared to second-order reference lines across four progressively finer resolutions.

Figure 9: Code slowdown: Comparison of GENE-X code slowdown for different number of blocks.

A secondary consideration when reducing the velocity space grid points is the corresponding performance scaling. Figure 9 depicts the slowdown of the GENE-X code which is basically the ratio of the runtime with and without BSG. This quantity is compared for different number of blocks. Usually the number of blocks for the target case will be limited to 3-5. A first observation from the plot is that the slowdown is generally greater than 1 which is due to the additional interpolation costs performed at the block boundaries. Further, we also observe that with increasing number of points the slowdown saturates between 1.2 - 1.4. However, we expect this number to go down since the targeted ITER case is supposed to be much finer than the test resolutions used here while keeping the number of blocks fairly constant. Therefore the ratio between the number of points in the poloidal plane that require interpolation and the total number of RZ points reduces.

3.3 Field solver optimization

The field solver in GENE-X, PARALLAX, handles the quasi-neutrality equations, the generalized Ampère’s law, and Ohm’s law on two-dimensional drift planes. These equations can be reformulated as elliptic Helmholtz-type equations of the form:

$$\lambda\phi - \xi\nabla \cdot (c\nabla_{\perp}\phi) = \rho, \quad (2)$$

where the perpendicular gradient is defined as $\nabla_{\perp} = \nabla - \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla)$, with \mathbf{b} denoting the unit vector along the magnetic field. The coefficients λ , ξ , and c are known functions, and ρ represents the charge density. These equations are discretized using finite difference methods and are solved using the flexible generalized minimal residual method (fGMRES), preconditioned with a geometric multigrid scheme.

3.3.1 AMD GPU Porting

In the previous development update, PARALLAX was successfully ported to NVIDIA GPUs by implementing a new CUDA C++ backend of the solver, PAccX, achieving a significant socket-to-socket speedup (approximately 20×) compared to the original Fortran-based CPU solver. In this update, substantial efforts have been dedicated to extending the portability of PARALLAX/PAccX to AMD GPUs. To accomplish this, we adopt the *hipify* approach [7], which enables porting the CUDA backend to AMD GPUs by redefining CUDA function calls as their HIP counterparts through a header file, e.g.,

```
#define cudaMalloc hipMalloc
#define cudaFree hipFree
#define cudaMemcpy hipMemcpy
#define cudaMemcpyHostToDevice hipMemcpyHostToDevice
...
```

We shall distinguish *hipify* from the *HIPIFY* [8] approach, which modifies the CUDA code to the HIP code with *hipify-clang* and *hipify-perl* provided by the ROCm library. By using the header-based *hipify* approach, we achieve multi-platform portability of the solver while maintaining a single code base, with CUDA as the primary backend. Any future development on the CUDA backend will automatically propagate to the HIP backend, provided that corresponding functions are available in ROCm/HIP. In cases

where no equivalent functionality exists, we will rely on third-party libraries that are compatible with both backends.

3.3.2 Matrix reordering optimization

While the updated field solver runs on both NVIDIA and AMD GPUs, we have observed a significant performance gap on AMD GPUs, despite comparable hardware specifications. For example, in a large circular test case with 37,679,076 grid points, the solving time for the CUDA backend on an NVIDIA A100 GPU is 2.09 s, whereas the HIP backend on an AMD MI250X takes 3.02 s.

By profiling the field solver, we identified that the performance difference between the CUDA and HIP backends is primarily caused by the Gauss–Seidel red-black kernel in the multigrid preconditioner, which accounts for approximately 80% of the total computation time. The original mesh ordering results in a staggered memory access pattern for the red-black kernel, which is suboptimal for GPU acceleration. The AMD MI250X is more severely affected by this discontinuous memory access than the NVIDIA A100, due to its smaller L2 cache size. To address this issue, we reorder the matrix according to the red-black partition, ensuring that grid points of the same color are stored contiguously in GPU memory (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Sparsity pattern of the original mesh ordering and red-black ordering.

Table 4 presents the performance comparison of the A100 and MI250X GPUs, with and without red-black reordering. As shown, adopting the GPU memory-friendly red-black ordering yields a greater speedup on the HIP-MI250X backend ($\times 1.65$) than on the CUDA-A100 backend ($\times 1.30$), thereby significantly narrowing the performance gap between HIP and CUDA from 44.5% to 13.6%. The HIP-MI250X backend benefits more from the matrix reordering than the CUDA-A100 backend due to the fact that MI250X has smaller L2 Cache (16 MB) than A100 (40 MB). As a result, the MI250X relies more heavily on coalesced and continuous memory accesses to maximize cache efficiency and minimize memory latency.

Table 4: Performance comparison with and without red-black reordering

	Original (s)	Red-black reordering (s)	Speedup
NVIDIA A100	2.09	1.61	1.30
AMD MI250X	3.02	1.83	1.65

3.3.3 Multi-GPU parallelization

To further improve the scalability of the field solver, we explore the possibility of solving the field equations in parallel using multiple GPUs. Preliminary efforts have been conducted on AMD hardware using `rocALUTION` [9], a sparse linear algebra library designed for fine-grained parallelism on the ROCm platform. We developed a standalone unit test program that reads the raw matrix and right-hand side (RHS) data from an ITER-scale test case (approximately 11 million grid points) and solves it using `rocALUTION`. The matrix is initially scaled by its diagonal entries and then solved using the BiCGStab linear solver, preconditioned with the classical Ruge–Stüben algebraic multigrid method. The strong scaling results of this test case on 1 to 8 MI250X GPUs are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Multi-GPU strong scaling with `rocALUTION` for the ITER-size test problem.

As shown in Figure 11, the general out-of-the-box parallelism provided by `rocALUTION` still falls short of ideal scaling. To address this, we plan to enhance the multi-GPU performance by developing a customized communication pattern tailored to the specific matrix structure of our problem.

4 Current Status of Gap Analysis

This section deals with the progress of the code GENE-X towards the target challenge. All of the described code improvements of the last section help in reducing the runtime of the code and makes it possible to further close the gap to the target FOM, although not all of them can be used together at the moment. The Figure of Merit (FOM) has

been defined in the proposal and in previous deliverables to be

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{\text{Time per time step} \times \text{total stream BW}}{\text{FP size} \times \text{total number of grid points full}}$$

where the "total number of grid points full" stand for the number of grid points that would be necessary without algorithmic changes like block-structured grids, which substantially reduce the number of needed grid points.

4.1 Target test case

The envisaged target test case definition did not change. We will simulate the turbulence in the edge and the Scrape Off Layer (SOL) of the ITER tokamak. GENE-X uses a Cartesian grid in the poloidal RZ-planes and a discrete number of poloidal planes along the toroidal direction. For the planned ITER runs, we estimate that at least 48 millions points are needed in the poloidal RZ plane and 32 of these poloidal planes are needed to discretize along the toroidal direction. For the velocity space we plan to use ≈ 80 points in v_{\parallel} (without BSG first, for BSG advantages see later) direction and ≈ 20 in μ direction. With two species as in the GENE case, this multiplies to a total of roughly 5 trillion points ($4.9 \cdot 10^{12}$).

We have to run the simulation long enough to have good statistics in the turbulent phase. For this we expect 50k to 100k time steps. As all timesteps are nearly equivalent in runtime, we only run 10-100 timesteps for the performance assessment runs in this section.

4.2 Reduced test case

For assessing the performance of the code, we have to run a reduced test case, that still contains all the relevant physics (at least the same code paths as with the target case), but is much less resource-intensive.

As in all the previous deliverables D1.2 and D1.6, we are using the following reduced case for GENE-X, which is roughly a factor 800-1000 smaller than the target case. We use a grid spacing in RZ of $9 \cdot 10^{-4} L_{\text{ref}}$ (with $L_{\text{ref}} = 6.41327m$) which leads to 339411 RZ points. Instead of 32 poloidal planes we use only 16 and also in v_{\parallel} and μ direction we reduce by a factor of 2 each to 40 v_{\parallel} points and 10 μ points. We still use 2 species to cover the same physics.

We tried to weak scale the test case up to the target values for the dimensions φ , v_{\parallel} and μ but keep the RZ points constant. Starting with 8 nodes of the MPCDF's VIPER-GPU machine (each node is equipped with two AMD MI300A APUs) we scale up to 64 nodes and get the results shown in Table 5.

The scaling from 8 to 16 nodes in the φ direction is fine, but then a big jump happens for larger cases. This is a clear indication that something is not working correctly in this architecture.

Doing the same runs on the Raven system at MPCDF, which is equipped with four A100 for each node and running the fieldsolver on the CPU, we get a decent weak scaling as shown in figure 13.

Table 5: Weak scaling.

RZ	φ	v_{\parallel}	μ	species	MPI	nodes	Time per timestep
330661/1	16/2	40/2	10/2	2/2	16	8	12.66
330661/1	32/4	40/2	10/2	2/2	32	16	11.19
330661/1	32/4	80/4	10/2	2/2	64	32	73.47
330661/1	32/4	80/4	20/4	2/2	128	64	63.60

Figure 12: Breakdown of a weak scaling on VIPER-GPU for the reduced test case. The fieldsolver is executed on the GPU and the data is passed via device pointers from GENE-X to PARALLAX/PAccX.

In the last column of Table 6, you can find the computed Figure of Merit of the runs. It is around 20000 which is still a factor of 3 too high compared to the target FOM of 6000. As we can see from the graph, a big part of the runtime goes into the fieldsolver, which has been ported to GPU already, but the combination of the two codes does not yet work fine.

4.3 Extrapolation

Extrapolation of the results from the reduced test case to the target case on an Exascale system is a difficult task. Especially because we do not know how the scaling develops on a larger scale.

We start from the reduced test case on 16 VIPER-GPU nodes which shows a time per timestep of 11.2s. One VIPER-GPU node has a performance of roughly 100TFlops/s. For reaching Exascale, one would need a total of 10000 of these kind of nodes with 2

Table 6: A breakdown of different code parts with the scaling is shown in figure 12.

nodes	timestep	exchange	static	coll	Ohm	Maxwell	Allreduce	Barrier	FOM
8	11.180	3.192	0.872	1.127	0.739	5.624	0.929	0.518	19895
16	11.989	3.375	0.872	1.509	0.832	5.798	1.401	0.657	21334
32	12.338	3.382	0.834	1.631	0.883	6.012	1.394	0.824	21955
64	12.152	3.386	0.834	1.910	1.017	5.416	1.809	0.898	21625

Figure 13: Weak scaling on Raven with 4 A100 per node. The fieldsolver is executed on the CPU.

MI300A each, hence a total of 20000 MI300A.

On the problem side we have to scale up a factor of 400 to come to the target case. With the (naive) assumption of ideal scaling, we would come to a time per timestep of the target case on an Exascale system of $11.2s \cdot \frac{400}{10000/16} = 7.2s$. The FOM does not change by ideal scaling.

4.4 Estimation of Compute Resources for the Target run

In the last year of the project, we are planning for the simulation runs for the target case. To get some more realistic estimation of the compute resources needed for these runs, we try to get these number from the FOM measured and the one we aim for.

Taking the results of the last subsection 4.3, we can estimate the needed compute resources to do the target run on a suitable system. We need 100000 timesteps of 7.2s on 20000 MI300A (or equivalent), this is a total of 200 hours on 20000 MI300A or 4 million GPU hours.

This large amount of computing resources will decrease in the same way as the FOM decreases in the follow-up on this project. Hence, for the target case with a FOM < 6000, we should end up with around 1.2 million GPU hours.

To become more concrete, we estimate the needed resources on LUMI-G, MareNostrum 5 and Jupiter, assuming ideal scaling (which is not given at the moment). So all of the numbers are just rough estimates.

	VIPER-GPU	LUMI-G	MN5	Jupiter
FP64 peak perf. 1 node	100T	128T	157T	167T
mem bw per node	7.2T	10T	10T	12T
# nodes full machine	16	2978	1120	6000
time per timestep (red.)	11.2			
time per timestep (full)	4480	17	46	7.2
node-hours needed (current,ideal)		1.4M	1.4M	1.2M
node-hours needed (target,FOM)		420k	420k	360k
available in recent call		1.8M	580k	4.7M

But we can already with these numbers see that one production run of the target case needs a considerable amount of the available computing time on the largest EuroHPC machines. And it becomes even more clear that we have to reach at least the FOM promised. Ideally we will go below the FOM of 6000 substantially.

5 Revision of Roadmap

From the weak scaling runs we can see that we need further development to overcome the still existing gap. The most obvious problem is the bad scaling of the field solver with the velocity space processes, which is an inherent problem of (gyro-)kinetic plasma simulations and comes from the 3D nature of the field equations.

Next is that the GPU code has still potential to be optimized, our kernels do not yet reach the roofline of the GPUs used and also the occupancy metric is quite low.

Finally, by porting the block-structured grid approach to GPU, we can use it for the target case. This would decrease the number of velocity space points and speed up the time to solution.

5.1 Partial MPI-Parallelization of the Fieldsolver

Although the problem might become less prominent due to optimizations on the field-solver itself, we still need a moderate parallelization of the update and solve step over the (unused) velocity space processes. To come to a large number of GPUs used, as necessary for Exascale runs, we have to highly parallelize GENE-X in the velocity space directions. Unfortunately, this parallelization is usually across nodes, because the innermost φ -direction is parallelized first.

A full parallelization is not advised as then the local problem might become too small for one GPU, so we aim at a moderate parallelization level of 4-8 MPI processes. However, the final setup has to be determined by performance measurements of the optimized code.

So, the next steps would be

1. Further assess the library solution with `rocalution` on AMD GPUs and with the `ginkgo`[10] library as a portable solution.
2. Use the MPI parallelization in these libraries to parallelize over the velocity space processes from GENE-X
3. Assess performance of these runs and find the “sweet spot” of parallelization level

5.2 Overall Optimization of the GPU code of GENE-X

We have a well performing GPU code now, but it is not yet very reliable on different architectures. Also the usage of the GPU ported PARALLAX/PAccX library is not yet always working. In addition the `op_rhs_static` kernel is quite large and does still have optimization potential for faster execution on the GPUs.

So the next steps here are

1. Stabilize the GPU code on the two main architectures for NVIDIA and AMD GPUs. Target systems here are MPG's computers RAVEN and VIPER-GPU but also LUMI-G and MareNostrum 5.
2. Measure kernel performance of the most time-consuming kernels on these architectures and optimize the kernels
3. Integrate the MPI-parallelized PARALLAX solver
4. Integrate the GPU ported block-structured grids

5.3 Porting BSG of GENE-X to GPU

With regard to the upcoming/remaining work, we plan to target two major milestones. First, we would like to perform code validation of GENE-X using BSG. For this, we intend to perform simulations with TCV-X21 configuration which has been well validated using GENE-X [4]. Finally, we plan to port the BSG implementation to GPU. This makes it then possible to combine all of the achievements in the project in the target run. We expect a reduction in points for the ITER case of 4-6 (we will not get the full factor of 10, because in general a higher velocity space resolution is advisable in these runs, but were not possible without BSG). This would come with a reduction in the runtime by a factor 3-4 \times and simultaneously reduce the FOM by the same factor.

6 Conclusion

We presented the recent code developments and how they aim at reaching the target simulations. Making use of available GPUs is the main part which has been followed in the GPU porting of GENE-X and PARALLAX and successfully reached for both of them independently.

On the numerical side, we finalized the implementation of a CPU version of the block-structured grids for GENE-X which promised a reduction in runtime of a factor 3-4. Validation in a larger run is now necessary and then a porting of these changes also to GPU and integration with the rest of the GENE-X GPU code.

In the project we reached now a state where all developments on their own did quite well progress and in the remaining time we have to focus on optimization and integration of all of these developments into a common simulation. Only then, we will be able to reach the promised Figure of Merit.

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